

Research Proposal

How does GPS impact our privacy?

By CHAIMAA BOUHDID

How Does GPS Impact Our Privacy?

Introduction

The concept of privacy according to the Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy defined as the ability to control access to one's personal information and to live one's life free from surveillance, intrusion, and judgement by others(10) has been recognized as a fundamental human right (11). To elaborate, the significance of privacy is demonstrated in the fact that all of the major agreements that define human rights include references to privacy or similar concepts. A list of similar documents may be found in APF(2006) (12) and the European Convention on Human Rights (11).

Fueled by news reports of potential privacy violations on the Internet, privacy has become one of the top issues among global customers (1). The Global Positioning System (GPS) is one new technology that has privacy advocates concerned. It is a navigation system that uses satellite technology (3). Its basic approach comprises measuring the distances between the receiver and a few simultaneously viewed satellites, and the satellite positions are predicted and broadcasted to the user together with the GPS signal (3) as well as other parties which might impact privacy in some ways (1).

GPS is an intrinsically intriguing study topic since it has become a vital part of our daily life. It is utilized in navigation systems, cellphones, transportation, agriculture, outdoor sports, and even animal tracking, among many other applications that will be discussed more below. Furthermore, GPS technology is continually evolving, making it even more intriguing to research. Researchers are finding new approaches to improve GPS performance, which opens up an interesting potential for innovation. Other intriguing aspects of GPS include its environmental and societal influence. It is an evolving and ever-changing field with much potential for research and study.

This research proposal is structured as follows: we will present the literature review on the link between GPS and Privacy, we will then develop our research questions and hypotheses, then we will present the methodology and data we will use to answer them, the following section will be focused on how we will access the data that will be used during the research, how we will deal with the ethical part of the research including the copyrights, the last section will be the research timeline.

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Research Statement

GPS has evolved over the last few decades to the point that it is now understood even by children (3). GPS enables software engineers to develop applications that use location data to provide services such as directions like Google Maps for example or ride-hailing apps like Uber and InDrive that can track the location of drivers and passengers, and provide real-time updates on the estimated time of arrival (22). Moreover, a lot of Geolocation applications like weather forecasts web applications use GPS technology to determine the location of the user, allowing the application to provide personalized content or services based on their location (23).

Furthermore, has been widely used in a variety of fields, including air, marine, and land navigation. GPS has become indispensable in business, research, education, and daily life due to its vast range of applications (1). Further to that, GPS increases productivity in a wide range of industries, including farming, construction, mining, surveying, package delivery, and logistical supply chain management (4). Another use of GPS is for understanding the factors determining the distribution and movements of animals around the landscape as it is a major objective for scientists, and conservationists (15).

Yet, a report by the National Insurance Crime Bureau (NICB) found that thieves are using GPS devices to locate and steal expensive assets such as vehicles and boats (21). GPS can also be used by abusive partners to track people without their consent as the Family lawyer Catherine Leach, of Leach Legal in Perth said (17). An abuser, for example, may use GPS to track where you've been and subsequently use that knowledge against you (16) which will have psychological impacts on the victims according to a study by Xu and Fung (2018). They found that individuals who were monitored with GPS tracking devices reported higher levels of anxiety and lower levels of satisfaction with their daily routines (19, 17).

This research study analyzes the many applications of GPS technology, primarily focusing on privacy issues. Its goal is to thoroughly investigate how various GPS applications, such as navigation systems may breach personal privacy. The research will look into how GPS data collecting, storage, and sharing procedures may violate individuals' privacy rights. It will investigate the dangers and vulnerabilities connected with these applications, such as location tracking, breaches of data, and illegal access.

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Research Question

The information era has brought the world closer together in only a few decades (3). But the advent of new technologies has brought with it an all-too-familiar challenge: how GPS technology impacts our privacy? To elaborate, this research aims to explore how GPS impacts our privacy, including the potential risks and benefits of using GPS technology. The research aims to examine the impact of GPS on various aspects of our lives, such as personal security, and data privacy. This leaves us to two sub research questions: What are the potential risks and vulnerabilities associated with GPS tracking that may compromise privacy? And how does GPS data collection and usage affect individuals' privacy rights and personal freedom? This study's hypotheses are whether GPS impacts privacy negatively or positively.

Literature Review

Opinions on the impact of GPS on privacy are divided between pessimistic and optimistic views. This first position was shared by Samuel Warren and Louis Brandeis as they published words that still ring true today in their iconic 19th-century law review essay on privacy (1): "The intensity and complexity of life... have rendered necessary some retreat from the world... so that solitude and privacy have become more important to the individual; but modern enterprise and invention have, through invasions upon [a man's] privacy, subjected him to mental pain and distress, far greater than could be inflicted by mere bodily injury".

Furthermore, The American Civil Liberties Union mentioned that GPS tracking can be used to monitor individuals' movements without their consent or knowledge. This can be done by installing GPS tracking devices in cars or other objects, or by using GPS-enabled smartphones (7) as modern devices are inexpensive, can be attached to a vehicle quickly, and have a long battery life (20). Such tracking can be used for various purposes, including surveillance by law enforcement (25, 8). But because investigators often track without a warrant, privacy advocates say the tactic threatens to monitor innocent people as well (20). As an example, the police suspected Antoine Jones of drug violations and tracked his movements continuously for one month by installing a GPS device on his car without a warrant (9).

Moreover, This kind of tracking is extremely invasive (6), because if the government knows where you are, it knows who you are. As the Jones appellate court explained in its ruling that the government violated the Fourth Amendment, "A person who knows all of another's travels can deduce whether he is heavy drinker,

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an associate of particular individuals or political groups – and not just one such fact about a person, but all such facts.”(8)

Finally, GPS can also be used for stalking and harassment. To elaborate, GPS technology can be used to track someone's movements without their consent, which is illegal in American law according to the National Conference of State Legislatures (13). A study conducted by the National Network to End Domestic Violence (14) found that abusers are increasingly using GPS devices to track their victims.

On the other hand, the second position that views GPS in an optimistic view was shared by many. To start with, GPS technology is used by emergency services such as police, fire, and ambulance to quickly locate and respond to emergencies. When a person calls 911, the GPS coordinates of their location can be used to determine their exact position. This information can then be used to dispatch emergency responders to the scene quickly and efficiently (24).

In addition to 911 calls, GPS technology can be used to create detailed maps of emergency response areas (24), which can help emergency responders find their way around quickly and efficiently, this is usually used in navigation and routing. To elaborate, GPS can provide real-time and accurate positioning information to emergency response vehicles, enabling them to navigate efficiently and choose optimal routes to the fire scene (28). Additionally, GPS can enhance the safety and accountability of fire response personnel. GPS devices can track the movements and locations of firefighters, ensuring their safety during firefighting operations (29).

Furthermore, GPS can help in keeping children safe through the use of location tracking. Sex offenders who are placed on GPS monitoring can be required to wear an ankle bracelet which allows their movements to be tracked in real-time. This can be especially useful in ensuring that sex offenders comply with court-imposed restrictions, such as staying away from designated "safe zones" like schools, parks, or other places where children congregate (5).

Lastly, GPS technology allows caregivers or family members to track the location of elderly individuals, especially the ones with Alzheimer's disease. This can help prevent wandering, which is a common behavior among individuals with Alzheimer's and can lead to dangerous situations such as getting lost or falling. With

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GPS tracking, caregivers can feel peace of mind knowing that they can monitor the location of their loved ones with no issues (6).

Empirical Review

The study, titled "A systematic review of the evolution of GPS use in active living research: A state of the evidence for research, policy, and practice" (30), looks into the use of GPS technology in comprehending the connection between physical contexts, social situations, and all levels of activity in free-living circumstances among people of all ages. The introduction discusses the significance of knowing the link between exercising and its health consequences, as well as the possibility of GPS technology to improve our understanding of this relationship.

The study used a systematic review method, using an extensive search strategy of six databases to locate peer-reviewed publications published between October 15, 2019, and October 15, 2020. Studies that used GPS technology to study the interaction between physical surroundings, social environments, and all levels of exercise in free-living situations across all age groups met the inclusion requirements. 129 studies satisfied the inclusion criteria out of the 2026 articles found. The quality of the research was assessed, and the data were combined using a narrative technique.

The study discovered that GPS has advanced significantly over the last decade, and the majority of studies used cross-sectional designs. Almost the majority of the studies were carried out in high-income nations, with no research carried out in countries with low or middle incomes. One of the study's shortcomings is that it only looked at peer-reviewed papers and excluded studies that used technologies other than GPS, such as worn cameras and it only mentioned limited uses of GPS.

Lastly, this is the first systematic review to look at how GPS is utilized to further comprehend the connection between physical contexts, social settings, and all levels of activity in free-living conditions across all age groups. GPS technology has advanced significantly during the last decade, and future trends indicate to the use of GPS in citizen-owned cell phones to promote active living research, policy, and practice.

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Research Gap

This research will be conducted as the present research about GPS and Privacy is lacking because of the unclear and random uses mentioned of GPS, which are the major concerns (3) for people who are interested in knowing how and to what extent GPS impacts their privacy. Different issues arose because of the latter as more privacy advocates are concerned (31, 20). To address such issues, this research will state exactly how GPS is impacting privacy, using reliable and trustworthy sources that will be helpful not only to people who are concerned about their privacy but to everyone for whom GPS has sparked an interest.

Methodology

To start with, I will utilize the deductive method in my research. I intend to begin with proven privacy and technology ideas and theories. These principles cover topics including data privacy, surveillance, information dissemination, and the advantages of GPS technology. GPS uses, for example, will provide benefits such as navigation help, location-based services, and emergency response. On the other side, I anticipate finding privacy issues related to GPS, such as potential data breaches, tracking, and loss of anonymity. By evaluating survey results from my participants, I will collect data to support or contradict the findings generated from the deductive reasoning process by constructing survey questions that match the deductive framework.

Moreover, I plan to use a systematic review as a secondary data source. The systematic review approach is perfectly suited to my research question because it diminishes bias and increases the accuracy of the study. Additionally, using a systematic review will guide me through the research topic to have more questions that will be addressed by conducting an anonymous survey with GPS users, the participants' personal data won't be shared nor mentioned, they will be aware of the study's aim, risks, and rights, informed consent will be obtained from them. . The survey will have 5 open questions and 5 questions that will be answered using a yes or no answer and it will be directed to 500 people as I need 100 respondents, with the expectation that 20% of those invited will actually respond. Thus, 500 people will be invited ($100 \text{ respondents} \div 20 \text{ response rate} = 500 \text{ invitations}$).

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To gather participants, I will use a non-probability sampling approach. To achieve a response rate of more than 20%, participants will be chosen depending on their availability. Furthermore, I intend to ensure variety among participants by selecting people from various backgrounds and nations throughout the world. A minimum of 50 people will be interviewed and asked questions about their availability and origins during these interviews to determine their fit for the study. This thorough selection procedure will provide a high level of confidence that the final sample will be made up of people from various backgrounds, assuring the validity and trustworthiness of the data obtained. Participants will also need to fill “Participants Form” to ensure a reply once they get the survey questions. The survey will be created using [TypeForm](#) and will be shared via email, LinkedIn and other social media platforms. For the survey’s questions, you will find the questions below:

Open Questions:

1. How often and for what reasons do you use GPS-enabled devices in your everyday life?
2. How has GPS technology enhanced your navigation experience or made your life easier?
3. Are you concerned about the possible privacy implications of GPS technology? Please expand on those concerns.
4. Have you ever thought that your privacy was put at risk as a result of the usage of GPS technology? If yes, please explain the situation.
5. How do you think GPS technology should be properly controlled to preserve people's privacy while yet enabling it to be useful?

Questions with a yes/no answer:

6. Do you allow websites to track your location? If yes, are you aware that they might use it for WI-FI triangulation or IP geolocation which can potentially enable targeted attacks or tracking?
7. Are you aware of the data-gathering procedures used by your GPS-enabled devices or applications?
8. Would you be prepared to give up some privacy in exchange for improved GPS accuracy or more services or features?
9. Do you think GPS technology should come standard with privacy safeguards?
10. Should GPS users have a greater say over how their location data is collected and used?

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For the analysis, both quantitative and qualitative analysis methodologies will be used. To examine numerical data and give statistical perspectives into participants' privacy experiences and issues, quantitative analysis will be utilized. However, qualitative analysis will be used to capture the breadth and depth of participants' privacy experiences, perspectives, and concerns. This method will entail assessing open-ended survey responses as well as qualitative data from the systematic review's chosen papers. By integrating statistical patterns with rich contextual insights, this study will get a more thorough knowledge of the impact of GPS on privacy by applying both quantitative and qualitative analysis methodologies.

Access

To find relevant academic publications, journals, and research papers pertaining to my topic, I will mostly use online libraries and databases such as IEEE, Science Direct, and Springer. These internet tools will supply me with a lot of knowledge and will enable me to study and analyze current material in order to provide a firm basis for my research.

Ethics

It is critical to highlight ethical considerations in a research paper, such as respecting intellectual property rights, gaining informed permission, and preserving privacy. To avoid a violation, I will:

- Ensure that research volunteers are completely aware of the study's aim, risks, and rights, informed consent must be obtained from them.
- Respect privacy by anonymizing data and securing sensitive information.
- Evaluate the research's larger ethical implications, such as its possible influence on communities or vulnerable groups, and to perform the study in a culturally sensitive and fair manner.
- Obtain authorization from institutional review boards (IRBs) or any relevant ethics committees.

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Research Timeline

The figure below represents the timeline of my research paper, a better version will be submitted along with the research proposal.

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5. Pre-test the survey questions: in case participants find some survey questions too personal so we can make changes if applicable.
6. Finalize survey questions.
7. Share survey questions via whatever social media platform participants are using then I will start data collection.
8. Data cleaning: remove any unnecessary data that is not related to the research question from the participants' answers.
9. Data Analysis using quantitative and qualitative approaches as mentioned in the methodology section.
10. Interpretation: project the survey's findings on the report.
11. Revision.
12. Edit the research paper.
13. Get feedback.
14. Finalize and submit.

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